

Union of 3-Total Difference Cordial Graph with the Bistar $B_{n,n}$

V. Arumugam¹ and K. Sangareswaran²
^{1,2} Department of Mathematics
 P.S.R Engineering College, Sivakasi-626140,
 Tamilnadu, India.

Abstract:- Let G be any graph with p vertices and q edges. We construct a map f on the set of all vertices of G to the set $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, k - 1\}$ where $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $k > 1$. If the edges are labelled by the absolute difference of the labels of their end vertices then f is said to be a k -total difference cordial labeling of G if $|td_f(i) - td_f(j)| \leq 1$ for all $i, j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, k - 1\}$ where $td_f(r)$ denotes the total number of vertices and the edges labeled by r . If a graph has a above mentioned labeling then it will be called as k -total difference cordial graph. In this paper we discuss the nature of 3-total difference cordial labeling of union of bistar with a 3-total difference cordial graph.

Keywords:- Union of Graphs, Corona Graphs, Bistar and Comb.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this manuscript we discuss only simple undirected graphs. In graph theoretic terminology, labeling is just to assign numbers, mostly, integers to the graph elements with some constraints. Graph labeling plays a vital role on many areas of computer science engineering and other fields of science [2]. Rosa introduced this concept with graceful labeling [6] in 1967. After that several labeling notions were introduced by numerous authors, see [2]. After two decades of Rosa’s notion, Cahit [1] initiated another important notion, namely cordial labeling. Ponraj et al. introduced k -total difference cordial labeling in [4]. In [4, 5], they studied 3-total difference cordiality of some graphs and are path, cycle, complete graph, star, bistar, comb, crown, armed crown, wheel, etc. and also they proved that every graph is a subgraph of a connected k -total difference cordial graphs. A graph whose vertex set V can be partitioned into two non-empty disjoint subsets (V_1, V_2) with the property that an edge of G joins a vertex of a V_1 to a vertex of V_2 . If each vertex of the former is adjacent with that of the later then we say that such a graph is called a complete bipartite graph. Generally, it is denoted by $K_{m,n}$, where the cardinality of the first set m and that of the second is n . If $m = 1$ then such a graph is called a star. A bi-star $B_{m,n}$ is a graph derived from two stars $K_{1,m}$ and $K_{1,n}$ by making adjacency with a vertex of degree m in $K_{1,m}$ with a vertex of degree n in $K_{1,n}$. The corona of two graphs is obtained by taking a graph to together with p copies of another graph, where p denote the number vertices in the former. Now, join each vertex of the former graph with all the vertices of its corresponding

copy of the later graph. Symbiotically if G and H be two graphs then their corona is denoted by $G \odot H$. Corona of a path with a trivial graph is called a comb graph. The disjoint union of two graphs is just taking union of their corresponding graph elements. In this paper we discuss the 3-total difference cordial labeling of union of a 3-total difference cordial graph with a bistar $B_{n,n}$. For more graph theoretic notions relevant to this manuscript, see [3].

II. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1. Consider a map f defined on the set of all vertices of a graph G to the set $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, k - 1\}$ where $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $k > 1$. For the edges of G , we put the absolute difference of the labels of their end vertices then the map f is known as k -total difference cordial labeling of G if the total number of vertices and edges labelled by the number r and not by r will differ by at most 1. We denote $td_f(r)$ as number of vertices and edges labelled by r . A graph consisting of the above labeling property is known as a k -total difference cordial graph and the map f is known as a k -total difference cordial labeling.

Here we recollect a result on bistar [4] which admits a new 3-total difference cordial labeling if and only if $n \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}$. Consider the bistar $B_{n,n}$. Let u, v be the central vertices of the two copies of the star. Let $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ be the vertices which are adjacent to u and $v_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ be the vertices which are adjacent to v .

Theorem 2.1. [4] The bistar $B_{n,n}$ is 3-total difference cordial if and only if $n \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}$.

Proof. It is noteworthy that the order and the size of $B_{n,n}$ are $2n + 2$ and $2n + 1$ respectively. According to the nature of the n , the proof is divided into three possible cases.

Case 1. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

Let $n = 3t$ where $t \in \mathbb{N}$. Suppose there exists a 3-total difference cordial labeling φ , then $td_\varphi(0) = td_\varphi(1) = td_\varphi(2) = 4t + 1$.

Subcase 1(a). $\varphi(u) = \varphi(v) = 0$.

If we assign the label 2 to any one pendent vertex then it will contribute two to $td_\varphi(2)$. It follows that $td_\varphi(2)$ must be an even number, an impossibility.

Subcase 1(b). $\varphi(u) = 0$ and $\varphi(v) = 1$.

To get $td_\varphi(0) = 4t+1$, a contradiction. Suppose $3t$ number of vertices v_i are labeled by 1 then $td_\varphi(2)$ must be an even number, a contradiction. In a similar argument, we can show that u and v cannot be labeled by 0 and 1 respectively in all the possible cases.

Subcase 1(c). $\varphi(u) = 0$ and $\varphi(v) = 2$.

As in subcase 1(b), we get $td_\varphi(1) < 4t + 1$ (or) $td_\varphi(1)$ must be an odd number. In either case, the map φ fails to be a 3-total difference cordial labeling.

Subcase 1(d). $\varphi(u) = \varphi(v) = 1$.

To get $td_\varphi(2) = 4t + 1$, two must be label of $4t + 1$ pendent vertices. Then $td_\varphi(1) > 4t + 1$, a contradiction.

Subcase 1(e). $\varphi(u) = 1$ and $\varphi(v) = 2$.

To get $td_\varphi(2) = 4t + 1$, the vertices $v_i, (1 \leq i \leq n)$ are labeled by zero and $t + 1$ vertices of u_i are labeled by 2. If it is so, $td_\varphi(0) < 4t + 1$. Similarly we can prove for all the possible cases that $td_\varphi(2)$ can never be equal to $4t + 1$, a contradiction.

Subcase 1(f). $\varphi(u) = \varphi(v) = 2$. Similar to subcase 1(d).

Case 2. $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

Let $n = 3t + 1$. Define a function f from $V(B_{n,n})$ to the set $\{0, 1, 2\}$ by $\varphi(u) = \varphi(v) = 0$,

$$\varphi(u_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq 2t + 1 \\ 0 & \text{if } 2t + 2 \leq i \leq 3t + 1 \end{cases}$$

and

$$\varphi(v_i) = \begin{cases} 2 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq 2t + 1 \\ 0 & \text{if } 2t + 2 \leq i \leq 3t + 1 \end{cases}$$

One can easily check that $td_\varphi(0) = 4t + 3$ and $td_\varphi(1) = td_\varphi(2) = 4t + 2$. This shows that φ is a 3-total difference cordial labeling.

Case 3. $n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$.

Let $n = 3t + 2$. As in case 2, assign the label to the vertices $u, v, u_i (1 \leq i \leq n), v_i, (1 \leq i \leq n)$. Then put the labels 1 and 2 to the vertices u_n and v_n respectively. It is easy to show that $td_\varphi(0) = 4t + 3$ and $td_\varphi(1) = td_\varphi(2) = 4t + 4$. Thus φ is a 3-total difference cordial labeling of $B_{n,n}$.

III. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we create a new 3-total difference cordial graph from a graph G which has already permits this labeling. This new graph is obtained by taking union of G with a bistar $B_{n,n}$. For, we utilize the Theorem 2.1.

Theorem 3.1. Let G be a (p, q) -3-total difference cordial graph. Then $G \cup B_{n,n}$ is 3-total difference cordial.

Proof. Let ψ be a 3-total difference cordial labeling of G . we define a map $f : V(G \cup B_{n,n}) \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2\}$ by

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \psi(x) & \text{if } x \in V(G) \\ \varphi(x) & \text{if } x \in V(B_{n,n}) \end{cases}$$

Now, we check whether the above mentioned labeling h is the required 3-total difference cordial labeling. For, we split up the proof into three cases.

Case 1. $p + q \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

Let $p + q = 3r$. In this case $td_\psi(0) = td_\psi(1) = td_\psi(2) = r$. The Table

1 given below ensures that h satisfies the requirements of a 3-total difference cordial labeling if $n \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}$.

Nature of n	$td_f(0)$	$td_f(1)$	$td_f(2)$
$n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$r + 4t + 3$	$r + 4t + 2$	$r + 4t + 2$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$r + 4t + 3$	$r + 4t + 4$	$r + 4t + 4$

TABLE 1. Constraints of h

Case 2. $p + q \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

Let $p + q = 3r + 1$. In this case we have the following possibilities:

- a) $td_\psi(0) = td_\psi(1) = r$ and $td_\psi(2) = r + 1$.
- b) $td_\psi(0) = td_\psi(2) = r$ and $td_\psi(1) = r + 1$.
- c) $td_\psi(1) = td_\psi(2) = r$ and $td_\psi(0) = r + 1$. Now, we divide this case into two subcases. Subcase 2(a). $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

If either (a) or (b) happens then the Table 2 shows that f is a 3-total difference cordial labeling.

Suppose (c) is true then we relabel the vertex v_n by 1. It is easy to check that f is a 3-total difference cordial labeling.

Subcase 2(b). $n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$.

Let $n = 3t + 2$. If (c) is true then $td_f(0) = td_f(1) = td_f(2) = r + 4t + 4$.

If (a) is true then we relabel f as follows: $f(u) = 0, f(v) = 2, f(v_i) = 0$ where $(1 \leq i \leq n)$ and $f(x) = \psi(x)$ for all $x \in V(G)$, and

Options	$td_f(0)$	$td_f(1)$	$td_f(2)$
(a)	$r + 4t + 3$	$r + 4t + 2$	$r + 4t + 3$
(b)	$r + 4t + 3$	$r + 4t + 3$	$r + 4t + 2$

TABLE 2. Constraints of f

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} 2 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq t \\ 0 & \text{if } t+1 \leq i \leq 2t+1 \\ 1 & \text{if } 2t+2 \leq i \leq 6t+5 \end{cases}$$

where $n \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$. Suppose $n \equiv 2 \pmod{6}$, then assign the labels as in the case that $n \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$. Then the remaining six vertices $u_{n-2}, u_{n-1}, u_n, v_{n-2}, v_{n-1}$ and v_n are labeled by 1, 1, 2, 0, 0 and 0 respectively. The Table 3 provide vertex and edge conditions of f .

Nature of n	$td_f(0)$	$td_f(1)$	$td_f(2)$
$n \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$	$r + 8t + 8$	$r + 8t + 2$	$r + 8t + 8$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{6}$	$r + 8t + 8$	$r + 8t + 4$	$r + 8t + 4$

TABLE 3. Conditions of f

Hence f is a 3-total difference cordial labeling.

Case 3. $p + q \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$.

Let $p + q = 3r + 2$. Then ψ must satisfy any one of the following conditions:

- a) $td_\psi(0) = td_\psi(1) = r + 1$ and $td_\psi(2) = r$.
- b) $td_\psi(0) = td_\psi(2) = r + 1$ and $td_\psi(1) = r$.
- c) $td_\psi(1) = td_\psi(2) = r + 1$ and $td_\psi(0) = r$.

We divide this case into two subcases. Subcase 3(a). $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

Let $n = 3t + 1$. If (c) is true then $td_f(0) = td_f(1) = td_f(2) = r + 4t + 3$.

If (a) is true then we reconstruct f as follows $f(x) = \psi(x)$ for all $x \in V(G), f(u) = 0, f(v) = 2$ and

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq 3t+2 \\ 2 & \text{if } 3t+3 \leq i \leq 6t+4 \end{cases}$$

$$f(v_i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq 2t+1 \\ 1 & \text{if } 2t+2 \leq i \leq 6t+4 \end{cases}$$

It is easy to check that $td_f(0) = td_f(1) = td_f(2) = r + 8t + 7$ and hence f is a 3-total difference cordial labeling, where $n \equiv 4 \pmod{6}$.

Suppose $n \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$ then take $n = 6t + 1$. Here we redefine f as

$f(x) = \psi(x)$ for all $x \in V(G), f(u) = 0, f(v) = 2$ and

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq 3t \\ 2 & \text{if } 3t+1 \leq i \leq 6t \end{cases}$$

$$f(v_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = 6t+1 \\ 0 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq 2t+1 \\ 1 & \text{if } 2t+2 \leq i \leq 6t+1 \end{cases}$$

In this case $td_f(0) = td_f(1) = td_f(2) = r + 8t + 3$. Hence f is a 3-total difference cordial labeling. Suppose (b) is true then we relabel as in the previous case. It is easy to verify that f satisfies the vertex and edge condition of a 3-total difference cordial labeling.

Subcase 3(b). $n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$.

Let $n = 3t + 2$. If either (a) or (b) is true then f is the required 3-total difference cordial labeling, see Table 4

Options	$td_f(0)$	$td_f(1)$	$td_f(2)$
(a)	$r + 4t + 4$	$r + 4t + 5$	$r + 4t + 4$
(b)	$r + 4t + 4$	$r + 4t + 4$	$r + 4t + 5$

TABLE 4. Vertex and edge conditions of f

For the case (c) $n \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$ or $n \equiv 2 \pmod{6}$ assign the labels to the vertices as in subcase 3(a). Then assign the labels 0 and 1 respectively to the vertices u_n and v_n . The Table 5 provides the existence of a 3-total difference cordial labeling f .

Nature of n	$td_f(0)$	$td_f(1)$	$td_f(2)$
$n \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$	$r + 8t + 8$	$r + 8t + 9$	$r + 8t + 8$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{6}$	$r + 8t + 4$	$r + 8t + 5$	$r + 8t + 4$

TABLE 5. Constrains of f

Hence, if $n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ then $G \cup B_{n,n}$ is a 3-total difference cordial graph where G is any 3-total difference cordial graph.

Q
Illustration 1. A 3-total difference cordial labeling of $(P_6 \odot K_1) \cup B_{7,7}$, where $P_n \odot K_1$ is a comb, is given in Figure 3.

Conclusion. In this study, we provide an idea that if we have a 3-total difference cordial graph then we can find another one by taking disjoint union with a bistar.

Fig 1. A 3-total difference cordial labeling of $(P_6 \odot K_1) \cup B_{7,7}$

REFERENCES

- [1]. I.Cahit, Cordial graphs:A weaker version of graceful and harmonious graphs,
- [2]. *Ars Combinatoria*, 23(1987), 201-207.
- [3]. J.A.Gallian, A Dynamic survey of graph labeling, *The Electronic Journal of Combinatorics*, 19 (2017) #Ds6.
- [4]. F.Harary, Graph theory, *Addision wesley*, New Delhi (1969).
- [5]. R.Ponraj, S.Yesu Doss Philip and R.Kala, k -total difference cordial graphs,
- [6]. *Journal of Algoorithms and Combutation*, 51(2019), 121-128.
- [7]. R.Ponraj, S.Yesu Doss Philip and R.Kala, 3-total difference cordial graphs,
- [8]. *Global engineering Science and Research*, 6(2019), 46-51.
- [9]. A. Rosa, On certain valuations of the vertices of a graph, *Theory of Graphs*
- [10]. (*Internat. Symposium, Rome, July 1966*), Gordon and Breach, N. Y. and DunodParis (1967) 349-355.